

The Influence of Industry 4.0; A Case study of Injection Molding Machine, Drone, 3D, Automobile, Aeronautic Factory

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ABSTRACT

Original equipment manufacturers (OEMs) are progressing toward smarter machines that can access more data when the factories are networked, thanks to the use of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning. The machines are capable of talking with one another and transmitting instructions along the production line, which can result in more efficient automated manufacturing processes.

In order to prepare for Industry 4.0, it is necessary to manage the short-term transfer of workplace skills while also developing a workforce with the futureproofed abilities that will be required. The fact that more young people are enrolling in tertiary education is encouraging, since it will ideally result in a greater interest in STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) professions as a result of Industry 4.0. Our ability to keep our curiosity and problem-solving mindset will be enhanced as we shift our work toward an emphasis on design as engineering. This move will pave the way for the emergence of new engineering positions. Many of these Industry 4.0 breakthroughs will continue to be driven by engineering, which will also help to solve some of the world's most intractable problems.

The fourth industrial revolution, or Industry 4.0, refers to the present trend of increased automation, digitalization, and data interchange in manufacturing technologies. Among other technological assets, it comprises cyber-physical systems, IoT, and cloud computing. Modern aircraft engines, with over 5000 sensors, generate up to 10 GB of data every second, exemplify what digitization and the Internet of Things could bring to the aviation industry as part of the upcoming Industry 4.0 revolution. This new age may improve major performance areas of air transport. This new era may mean a shift in safety improvement, especially in an industry where safety standards are high and improvement margins are tight. That is, cyber-physical systems are designed to aid humans in harsh or risky jobs, make judgments, and accomplish tasks autonomously. It highlights existing and prospective applications of Aircraft 4.0 to improve aviation safety, and how they might do so.

Keywords: INDUSTRY 4.0, AVIATION 4.0, DIGITIZATION, IOT, BIG DATA

Introduction

Consider the following scenario: your clients submit you a schedule, which is automatically brought in and

interpreted by a system, and the system then creates a production plan in the back end. On the digital workstations in the factory, this production plan is communicated. Deviations from the defined plan are noted and recorded [1,2].

The process parameters for the items in the schedule are pulled from a database, and software bots monitor the process parameters 24 hours a day, 7 days a week to guarantee they are followed. If there is any downtime, the affected individuals receive a text message on their phones instantly advising them of the downtime and asking them to take the appropriate actions.

Finally, at the end of the procedure, a finished products shop is created, allowing you to define your inventory in real time. Consider what would happen if the system generated all of the different types of reports and log sheets automatically, and the essential data was fed into your ERP in real time.

Consider a situation in which you are unable to visit your factory because you are traveling, but you can still stroll directly into the shop floor and check every detail on your phone.

We are living in the Fourth Industrial Revolution period, in which computers are connected to a platform that allows them to communicate with one another and, eventually, make choices without the need for human intervention. Smart factories are already a reality thanks to a combination of a tangible software platform and the internet of things (IoT) and internet of services (IOS) [3,4,5].

Components of Industry 4.0

IoT gateways, cyber-physical systems, factory digitalization, digital twins, IOS, condition-based monitoring, ERP and manufacturing execution system (MES) automation, robotic process automation (RPA), cybersecurity infrastructure, virtual and augmented reality, artificial intelligence (AI), neural networks, and machine learning are all examples of Industry 4.0.[6]

An increase in income, a reduction in operating costs, and an increase in asset efficiency are all examples of business goals. Planned and unexpected downtimes, quality rework, and process wastage are just a few of the obstacles we face due to a lack of awareness, responsibility, and manual interventions.

Industry 4.0 is projected to reduce downtime (35 percent -40 percent), enhance output (15 percent -20 percent), improve quality (35 percent -40 percent), improve total productivity (65 percent -70 percent), and improve asset utilization, according to case studies from our customer base (35 percent -40 percent).

Improvements in electricity utilization, overall cost reduction, avoidance of unnecessary capital expenditures, and waste reduction are among the other intended consequences [7,8,9,3].

- **Digital Twin:** The first step toward Industry 4.0 is to create a digital twin. A digital twin can be used to recreate the whole shop floor experience on a digital playground, revealing every tiny aspect and information flow. This aids in the detection of process bottlenecks and issues.
- **Preventive And Predictive Maintenance:** Factory maintenance plans may not always be sufficient since numerous external variables are not taken into account. The working conditions, offsets, and surroundings of the machines all play a role in maintenance.
- **Machine And Part History:** It's critical to know the history of the machine and part you're working on. Trends

can be built using historical data, allowing you to investigate the scope of improvement and modify your operations.

- **Operator Mapping:** Operator performance can be indexed and highlighted. Following safety rules and conducting cross-operator analysis can assist in identifying the asset and conditions that allow an operator to operate at their best.
- **Tool Life and Machine Health:** Tool life and machine health are vitally important. At regular periods, one must continue to monitor and derive the health of the asset purchased, as well as evaluate performance. Tool consumables and evaluating tool life are useful in not only optimizing the process but also assuring efficient cost utilization for each part produced. This provides a clear picture of the return on investment.
- **Real-Time Efficiency and OEE Analysis:** Postmortem monitoring of efficiency and overall equipment effectiveness (OEE) data does not help reduce problems that emerge during the shift. When this is done in real time, it allows for immediate corrective action, which saves the rest of the shift.
- **Downtime Analysis:** It's critical to comprehend and analyze the many causes of downtime. This can be investigated further in order to identify redundancies and optimize processes in order to reduce overall downtime.
- **Quality Control:** The first step in quality control is to keep track of operational parameters and offsets. After manufacture, ensuring that all checks are completed and the predispatch inspection is completed correctly will improve overall quality.
- **Production Planning:** An algorithmic production planning method can improve asset use. The received schedule must be entered into the system so that the asset's utilization can be planned automatically. The optimum plan can be dynamically created from the system for plan deviations using the relevant data inputs.
- **Condition-Based Monitoring (CBM)** is required for crucial parts that must be characterized in terms of temperature, pressure, and other physical factors. Bots that monitor circumstances in real time and alert when there is an anomaly will help to improve the process' overall quality and efficiency.
- **Report Automation:** There are several situations on the shop floor where different reports are manually prepared to keep track of various operations. With the help of digitization, these reports can be prepared automatically.
- **Robotic Process Automation:** The automation of numerous business processes helps to a factory that is more efficient overall. RPA, for example, can be used to automatically feed data from the shop floor into the ERP.

The Megatrends of Industry 4.0

There are some essential megatrends out there that stand out as crucial enablers of transition for the automotive sector. Some of them are [10,11,12,13]

Cloud Computing

Sharpening the output and excellence while reducing expenses has always been the main objective of all the process enhancements. Cloud stands out as one of those areas, which can highlight the starting of a brand-new era.

Here, the Internet of Things (IoT) will be utilized as a purchase puller and as a tool, which will improve the bottom-line performance of OEM and improve the internal savings. Latency and criticality will surely be the two main factors that will come into play when deploying cloud within an industrial setting.

The Role of Analytics

The analysis of Big Data is the starting of the amplified latent for the automotive sector, which will negate all the existing challenges and look way beyond customer expectations. Process improvements, customer behavior, resource optimization, and risk management are the top categories that all manufacturers should utilize for their data penetrations.

This approach will surely provide all the vehicle manufacturers with a view of the imminent trends, which will offer them guide investments and structure research. It will enable automakers to make data-driven decisions and pave the path to avoid all the associated risks and losses. By linking the production lines with the suppliers, the stakeholders will understand the interdependencies, process cycle times, and the flow of all the materials.

Industry 4.0 and Injection Molding Machine

A phased introduction of a new technology is effective for one simple reason: it accelerates change and allows all questions to be answered before the technology is rolled out to the complete crew. When firms roll out technologies too quickly, one of the biggest hazards is that the "change management" part of the technology is lost among personnel. There will be questions, some of which will be repetitious, some of which will have simple answers, and some of which will not. The manager's job is to run the business as efficiently as possible while also integrating a system that will provide staff with tools they've never had before.

Time is the biggest waste within every organization, as our industry grows increasingly focused on squeezing out inefficiencies in every aspect. While producing thorough data, an Industry 4.0 production monitoring system can fully minimize time spent collecting production measurements. Managers can swiftly detect root-cause production difficulties by having access to a multitude of data in real time. The control of the production system by management hinges on the return on investment (ROI). ROI monitoring becomes easier to analyze and respond to when employees are given new tools.

Phase 1: Begin small and work your way up. Build a strategy for successful integration with your Industry 4.0 system provider. Because the provider will need to know exactly what your monitoring objectives are, it's up to you to ask the right questions:

What is the best way for me to communicate the value to my employees?

What will happen to our IT infrastructure as a result of this?

How can I make sure the data is correct?

What are the most important metrics for each department?

Building an action plan with the supplier that contains key objectives to work on from a management perspective, such as:

New key performance indicators (KPIs) are being added, as well as measurables at the personnel level.

Begin by simply assigning new responsibilities to staff and rewarding them for managing their portion of the

new software. Show them how, if it's maintenance resources, the system can warn them when a machine issue arises, resulting in a faster resolution time due to instant problem identification.

Keep in mind the following:

Demonstrate the benefits of time savings to your employees; push new incentives based on metrics gathered by the system; and reward problem identification sourced by the program.

Phase 2: Educate the department heads about the new tools and provide them with access to the most basic functionality first. Internally, promote the system and serve as a resource for them. Use your system supplier's relationship to your advantage, but don't rely on them for every answer - they don't know your employees as well as you do.

The following are some significant methods to employ:

Assign an internal champion to help administer the system from an administrator's standpoint. This individual should be the main point of contact for the system vendor.

Create your rollout team(s) and start small with particular KPIs. Create logins for each person of your department, for example. Request that each department use the new system to collect reports.

Gradually introduce more complex KPIs and devise a strategy for phasing out any outdated processes. This plan should be guided by your system supplier, who should be aware of these processes.

Your department heads should be well conversant in the system within one to two months and require no additional training.

Phase 3: The full implementation. It's time to start rolling out the system across the organization now that you've gotten buy-in from your department leaders. Assign each department head to be the system's expert in their area. You'll also have to keep track of how well each group's skills are being integrated under their supervision. Build reports on a regular basis, take advantage of new data, and inquire about how each employee is utilizing the system.

Work with your supplier to provide active input and fine-tune each component of the system so that it becomes more embedded in your employees' daily work lives.

Once the program is up and running, have the supplier assist you in calculating the ROI using your own data and presenting the results to your employees. Take advantage of this opportunity to incorporate your own KPIs and leverage their performance across the system. People will be able to actively use this data for their own job performance and gains in their daily work lives in this way [14,15.16.17].

Maintain the following important strategies:

Daily stand-up meetings (if applicable) should be centered on the system to ensure management understand its relevance.

Unfavorable patterns should be noticed and discussed as a team as soon as possible using the system. The system should also be used to determine resolution and impact.

Reward employees that assist management in identifying these tendencies and creating a pleasant atmosphere around the system. Use gamification, or game dynamics, to motivate staff to achieve their objectives and reward

them appropriately.

Above all, never utilize the system to embarrass someone in public. Any disciplinary action should always be done behind closed doors. Public shaming may cause people to have an unfavorable attitude toward new technology.

Ask employees about the system on a regular basis. Employee engagement helps to guarantee that it is updated and handled properly. The more integration that is built into the system, the more value it brings to the company's overall strategy.

In terms of production, plastic injection molding is a challenge. Using Industry 4.0 technology will offer a large amount of historical data in a short amount of time. Any company that is scientifically based needs to take this strategy. It will offer essential information on a regular basis to ensure a logical approach to standardization. The amount of informational data accessible and how quickly it is accessed determine the profitability of any business [18,19,20,13].

Fig. 1: The digital transformation framework for injection molding industry based on the double-helix model of three perspectives and nine dimensions.

Fig. 2: The five-dimension digital twin model.

Fig3: Network topology of the industrial Internet system for the company.

Industry 4.0 and Drone

Industrial drones are seen as the next big thing in the current Industry 4.0 revolution. Drones are also becoming more popular among businesses. Drones are capable of completing an increasing variety of Industry 4.0 jobs. Drones transport materials from storage to the production floor and final products from production to transportation. The labor costs are significantly reduced as a result of this technology. Drones are extensively employed in the telecom industry to conduct site audits quickly and effectively, providing top-down views and line-of-sight inspections (Beke et al., 2018; Kim et al., 2021). For marketing purposes, they can provide high-resolution pictures of residences. Drones can scan transmission lines, inspect boilers, monitor solar panels, and analyze and repair storm damage faster than humans. In terms of acquisition and maintenance, this technology provides a more cost-effective option to helicopter-based operations. Artificial intelligence (AI)-driven data analysis is being carried out as a result of the drones in order to improve the effectiveness of their high-precision monitoring systems [21,22,23,16,18].

Some of the most fascinating applications have come from the Internet of Things (IoT). Drones can extend a network's physical constraints by adding IoT endpoints to it. Because many corporate activities increasingly occur at the network's edge, this is a critical issue. As a result of drone technology, numerous mobile IoT devices' capabilities have been pushed into new areas at the edge. Drones have the ability to survey locations that are difficult to reach. In an IoT setting, an IoT drone might act as a mobile sensor, gathering data and transferring it to a cloud app or another analytics API service. Drones can thus be used as remote inspection devices to maintain IoT endpoints and other components. The automation industry and drone makers have been looking for high-speed data analytics combined with Industrial IoT, cybersecurity, and sensor-mounted drones as a revolutionary.

Inspection times have shortened from weeks to a few days without the requirement for work stoppages. Inspections of wind turbines yield similar effects, with shorter timeframes and lower costs. In terms of data collection, drone technology is both safe and cost-effective. Integrating this data into asset management and field service systems to produce actionable results generates real commercial value. It can help you save money, reduce downtime, and improve safety while increasing operational efficiency. Drones provide superior precision for constructing maps, quality control methods, and cost reductions than expensive tools for scanning industrial areas. Drones will become a necessary part of the building industry due to safety and compliance rules.

This technology not only changes the way business is done, but it also prioritizes employee safety. The use of self-driving drones to identify fires and gas leaks lowers the danger of workplace mishaps. Safety and inspection missions are done on a regular basis, which helps to increase industry safety standards. In a commercial drone, the user and controller are connected wirelessly, allowing for end-to-end communication. Like any other IoT device, it connects directly to an industrial control system, such as SCADA. Sensors are immediately connected to the utility's principal communication network, allowing them to communicate with one another. Integrating at this level necessitates the secure transport of data and imaging kinds. Drones and their important uses in Industry 4.0 are briefly discussed in this study.

The third industrial revolution includes electronics, the internet, nuclear energy, and biotechnology. Unlike the first industrial revolution, which was focused on mechanisation, Industry 4.0 is focused on automation and cyber-physical systems, which will eventually replace many types of human labor. Industry 4.0, the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), Big Data, and drones are all new technological tales that will undoubtedly collide. The introduction of self-driving drones has had a significant impact on how industrial enterprises operate. The contributions of drones to the Industry 4.0 revolution are catapulting businesses into the modern era of technology while also catapulting innovation to new heights. The pillars of Industry 4.0 are depicted in Figure 2[24,25,26].

In the manufacturing business, drones will be employed extensively for asset inspection and maintenance, intracompany material and part movement, and inventory taking. Inspection and maintenance will be the most common applications, as a drone equipped with various sensors, such as ultrasonic, laser, Lidar distance sensors,

chemical sensors, stability and orientation sensors, or stereoscopic cameras, can quickly detect anomalies or problems in industrial equipment. It's useful in refineries, pipelines, mines, and other large facilities where human inspection is either risky or useless due to the fact that not all regions can be visited. As a result, drones help to reduce the time, risk, and cost of human inspections. Drones will also be used in industry for intra-company transportation, or the movement of components or materials between one company's neighbouring locations. Drones fitted with barcode or RFID scanners that enforce the parts and communicate the data to the inventory management system, obviating the necessity for manual inventory taking, are another possible field of use[27].

Because of rapid technological advancement, consumers now have access to cutting-edge products at affordable costs. Because of their high costs and technical expertise, drones have generally been relegated to military usage. Consumers, on the other hand, may be able to purchase drones for less than \$100 due to economies of scale. Drones are expected to be worth \$127 billion in a variety of industries. Commercial drone use, for example, will have a greater influence on agriculture and infrastructure than on commerce.

Businesses and consumers will clearly benefit from the consequences. Consumers profit directly from the creation of new jobs, which leads to higher wages. Businesses will be able to save money by employing more cost-effective inventory, transportation, and distribution methods thanks to commercial drones. Lower prices can be passed on to customers as a result of these cost savings.

Fig 4: Pillars of Industry 4.0

Fig 5: Specific features of drones for Industry 4.0[28]

Industry 4.0 and 3D,

Although 3D printers were first introduced in the 1980s, they have become increasingly important in the fourth industrial revolution. The rise of 3D technologies, or additive manufacturing, has been aided by the use of automated processes and technology in various sectors and industries.

Companies are investing in this technology in order to increase product quality and stay ahead of the Industry 4.0 trend. Let's look at some of the advantages of 3D printing in the context of Industry 4.0. Prototypes of high quality. [29,30] The rapid prototyping method has benefited greatly from the advancement of 3D technologies. Advanced software now allows manufacturers to create complicated three-dimensional objects before moving on to mass production.

2. Speed of Printing

Prototypes are frequently required by R&D departments for new goods. 3D printing services help designers save time and money by speeding up the process.

The printers' speed has improved in recent years, and they can now customize parts in minutes. Engineers can make adjustments to the design more quickly if there are any.

3. The Effect on the Environment

Traditional production, often known as subtractive manufacturing, generates a lot of waste. Additive manufacturing, on the other hand, is a preferable option today that many countries are concerned about environmental conservation and decreasing carbon emissions.

3D printing creates items by combining several layers rather than removing waste. The printers may make a single duplicate using the most advanced technology, lowering the amount of unsold inventory. Some 3D printers may also print with recycled materials, lowering environmental impact and cutting waste.

4. Pricing and Costs

The cost of 3D printers is relatively high due to its effectiveness. Their market values are determined by the North American Academic Research, 4(11) | November 2021 | <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5789895> Monthly Journal by TWASP, USA | 230

intended use and material specifications. The cost of printers is falling in tandem with the rise in demand for fast prototyping. It's more cost-effective to invest in high-tech 3D printing for your clientele if you're interested in large-scale fast prototyping.

5. Printing Supplies

You can utilize a variety of materials in additive manufacturing, including plastic, wood, and metal. A vast variety of materials may be printed with 3D printers. As a result, depending on the needs of the client, the company may make high-quality parts in any material.

6. Technological Progress

In today's Industry 4.0, new software and digital updates are released on a regular basis. Due to their flexibility to grow with the latest technology, 3D printing services remain vital in industrial processes. 3D printers will become increasingly important in the future, particularly for rapid prototyping.

Fig 6: 3D printing is one of the tools used in completing rapid prototype processes/Image **Industry 4.0 and Automobile,**

Many people are perplexed as to why the automobile industry is being singled out for industry 4.0 and digital transformation. There's a good reason for that, and it's a significant one. Customer service requirements have risen considerably in a number of non-automotive businesses.

It's because these businesses are looking for ways to engage customers beyond automobiles. When it comes to time-to-market, product planning, and innovative services, OEMs miss out on chances. They are unable to do so due to a lack of car or customer feedback.

Direct contact between the vehicle/customer and the OEMs will enable the latter to fully comprehend and assess all client preferences. It will also allow OEMs to eliminate some inefficiencies in a painless manner.

The customer is similar to the Apple Store model in that all transactions are monetized. Manufacturers must

work hard to comprehend the pathways that will have a favorable impact on the bottom line and cost reductions. In today's world, connected automobiles are taking over the entire blue planet. They've risen to prominence as a hotspot for investment in the automobile industry. Information technology and telematics will soon manage all elements of automobile mobility.

Service diagnostics, navigation, multimedia, emergency, and security services are currently available in linked automobiles. These services have gotten far too broad, extending to both the home and the office.

As a result, automobile OEMs must consider restructuring their entire business and providing each of their consumers with an integrated mobility experience. Customers will be able to access a variety of different digital capabilities as a result of connected vehicles, which will change how they interact with and use the vehicles [23,26,28].

They also provide a plethora of options to revisit all revenue data in order to redefine, extend, and amplify client communication.

Techniques	Focus on condition of equipment
Classification	Classify the failure of machine in next '1day', or '1 week' or '1 month'? Accordingly label data i.e Normal instance Failure instance
Clustering	Try to make different cluster of data that get by sensor (e.g. ultrasonic or vibration sensors) like –heat, vibration, RPM etc.
Regression	Determine the remaining life an asset Problem is solved by applying regression technique.
Outlier detection	When data does not fit in any class it is highlighted as outliers.
Sequential pattern	Focus on identifying accurate pattern or abnormal, unusual or irregular patterns recovered by sensor.
Association Rules	In machine one part is related to another part if one is failure than another parts will be failure in near future is identify by applying association rules.

Industry 4.0 and Aeronautic Factory

The four impacts

Aeronautics has a responsibility to keep up with Industry 4.0 in order to meet the productivity problem it faces. It will gradually incorporate all new digital technologies, software, and materials in the next years, allowing it to build a new form of organization and new manufacturing methods.

Pascal Brier, Altran Group Executive Vice President, Strategy & Innovation, discusses the four fundamental developments brought on by Industry 4.0 in the aircraft manufacturing industry.

1. A distinctive data system (from the silo to cooperation)

Today, data pertaining to aircraft manufacture is frequently dispersed across many systems that are largely unconnected. This creates information islands surrounding Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP), specifically

administrative administration, the MES (Manufacturing Execution System), the production scheduling system, or the set of factory floor systems, sometimes known as the heart of factories, where parts are made. As a result, when a problem arises, the affected area of the factory is quarantined while data is sent up to the silos and a decision is made, slowing down production sequencing.

Industry 4.0's first impact will be to connect all of these silos in order to achieve vertical integration, or a continuous chain of data. Sensors will be put throughout the chain, sending data on production status, stock management, potential difficulties, and so on. This vertical integration will also assist something crucial: the ability to make decisions at the production floor's heart. "Industry 4.0 provides a real-time analysis capability of what is happening in the production thanks to the data supplied by the sensors, allowing for rapid reactions to any problems," explains Pascal Brier. This helps to eliminate the use of quarantine systems, which can seriously impede productivity.

2. Digital manufacturing technologies that are new

The arrival of new digital technologies is also a part of Industry 4.0.

To begin, the plant will use innovative production methods such as 3D modeling and additive manufacturing. These technologies will enable parts to be designed with less material, making them lighter, smaller, and hence less costly to manufacture.

As a result, production lines will be altered. For manufacturing start-up, they will be made up of smaller, more adaptable equipment. "Today, the custom is to equip oneself with some big machinery that employ numerous workers/companions full-time at the station to guarantee that everything is in working order and to stop production if there is even the tiniest fault."

"The entire connection will be affected in the future." It will be made up of a number of small digital machines with sensors that are connected to a control room in real time, allowing it to be directed remotely and providing greater flexibility. "This will revolutionize the way businesses invest," Pascal Brier says.

Finally, because all of these modern devices are digital, artificial intelligence can analyze their systems, reducing mistake rates and downtime. According to a McKinsey study, these new devices can lower quality costs by 10% to 20%, storage costs by 20% to 50%, and maintenance costs by 10% to 40%.

3. A centralized command center

If all of the machines on the production line are smart and connected, a massive amount of data will be generated, which the company will need to collect and analyze in order to react more quickly.

This entails the construction of control rooms that will collect data from several machines, if not multiple manufacturing sites. These centers will keep a real-time eye on the entire production chain and use data to help operators complete their responsibilities.

The data may be delivered via a mobile device, allowing decision-makers to keep an eye on their machines from anywhere at any time. "It's almost like you've got a factory in your pocket!" "Look," Pascal Brier says, tapping his smartphone, "there, I'm connected to a factory in Spain in real time." I have access to all of the machines' info."

These control rooms provide a number of advantages. They enable real-time visibility and the ability to remotely

control production, especially in the event of a breakdown. Above all, they allow for enhanced data analysis and, as a result, the construction of scenarios or simulations to see how productivity could be increased.

4. The interaction of man and machine

Industry 4.0 heralds the arrival of manufacturing floor automation. Collaborative robots, or "cobots," are designed to divide work between man and machine by entrusting the robot with the tedious aspects of the activity while leaving the decision-making to the man. This has real-world, positive implications for factory operations. "As a result, McKinsey believes that unit productivity per post might rise by 75%!"

Pascal Brier reminds us that "it's not only a productivity issue." "It's also a matter of security." Access to difficult or sensitive zones will also be possible with the use of cobots. They will be able to approach extreme heat sources, electrical zones, and other such areas, for example. As a result, we'll be able to move more quickly while also boosting worker safety on the job."

Aeronautics has already been disrupted by Industry 4.0. According to Pascal Brier, vertical manufacturing integration will be a reality by 2020. Something new, which will undoubtedly raise the stakes: "Without a doubt, cyber-security is the guarantor of Industry 4.0. Reflection on the security of digital data lies at the heart of our industry's evolution."

Parts and technicians ready

Augmented Work, maintenance and service

Fourth dimension facilitate guidance, remote assistance and documentation

Time of next Dispatch Condition occurrence.

Cockpit safety cognitive computing aid systems

"... the ability of computing systems to act like the human brain..."

- **Airbus cognitive computing applications:**
 - reduce the information overload pilots face during a crisis.
 - help guide pilots through catastrophic emergencies.
 - visual tools to help pilots identify the most pertinent information in cases of a disaster to aid them in making difficult decisions, while automating some of the less critical ones.
- **IBM's Watson Cockpit Mentor?**
 - IBM and Cornell **new chip:** energy-efficient spiking neural network.

Fig 8: Aviation safety cognitive computing applications.

Conclusion

The manufacturing industry is undergoing a remarkable fourth evolution, fueled by technological breakthroughs such as the Internet of Things (IoT), intelligent networks that connect machines, work, and systems, allowing them to independently exchange data and commands, initiate actions, and control one another. Intelligent products and smart manufacturing processes, as well as vertically and horizontally connected manufacturing systems, are at the heart of new manufacturing.

The notion is universal, even if it is renamed locally to reflect diverse initiatives taking place in various geographical areas and industry branches. In five years, experts predict that 85 percent of businesses will integrate Industry 4.0 solutions across all major business divisions. Only at the European level, it will be equivalent to an annual expenditure of €140 billion by 2020.

In terms of aviation, the most common uses of the Industry 4.0 idea so far have been robotics, additive manufacturing, augmented reality, IoT, and simulation in aerospace manufacturing processes. Aside from the issue of how safety is maintained at the manufacturing sites, the potential of Industry 4.0 key enabling technologies to raise the highly tight safety levels in aviation operations has not yet been addressed. This chapter examines the potential of Industry 4.0 core enabling technologies to improve commercial aviation's already stringent safety standards, as well as how the impending Aviation 4.0 (Industry 4.0 for aviation) could signal a paradigm change in safety improvement.

This chapter examines the stages of aviation development from basic VFR flying rules in Aviation 1.0 to Aviation 4.0, when cyber-physical systems will be developed to aid humans in physically demanding, unpleasant, or dangerous labor, making judgments, and completing tasks autonomously.

The authors identify four stages in the development of commercial aviation, which correspond to the four stages of the industrial revolution. The adoption of increased levels of automation on board aircraft is directly linked to these four stages. Flying evolved under visual flight rules, following visual indications and signals, and there was no instrumental aid to help pilots fly in the initial evolutionary stage, Aviation 1.0, which corresponded to the beginning of commercial aviation. The replacement of outdated mechanisms by electric technology

dominated the second stage, Aviation 2.0. The third stage of the commercial aviation revolution, Aviation 3.0, saw a major integration of technology in the cockpit. Finally, Aviation 4.0 is concerned with the development of cyber-physical systems (CPS) that can assist humans in their demanding work by assisting them in making autonomous decisions and completing tasks, as well as the integration of cyber-physical components into Future Aviation Information Systems. The Aviation 4.0 airframe will be a digital and smart airplane thanks to cyber-physical technologies.

Automation, IoT, AI, cognitive computing, big data analytics, digitization, and other Aviation 4.0 technologies have the potential to create a paradigm shift in the aviation industry, providing new mechanisms to make it not only more efficient but also safer. With the new tools made available by Aviation 4.0, firms and researchers are starting to discover hitherto unknown concepts and approaches to safety. Finally, the authors present six case examples of the use of the Aviation 4.0 idea to improve aviation safety, which is already a reality:

Automatic, rule-based flying under predetermined conditions.

Creating a reliable airplane predictive maintenance system.

Cognitive computing help solutions for cockpit safety.

Updated weather data in real time

Improved search and rescue services, particularly in distant or marine areas.

Real-time monitoring and warning of human performance based on nonintrusive physiological sensors/signals and contextual data.

This transformation, however, is not without its detractors. The certification of cyber security criteria for e-Enabled airplanes; the development of anti-tamper avionics hardware and software; and the collaboration of industry and governments to combat the cyber threat to aviation are all challenges related to information assurance and cyber security. Aerial operations have a number of significant technological obstacles, including the following:

Interoperability of global aviation networks, including signal processing and wireless performance, as well as aircraft Internet interfaces;

Verification and validation of onboard software, awareness of cyber-physical life-cycle scale, and how to protect end-to-end whole SW supply processes

Utilizing sensor networks and data fusion, information management and data analytics, vital real-time data sharing, proper end-to-end information interchange, and distributed decision-making to improve airplane health, control, and prognostics; and lastly,

Visualization, keeping the person in the loop, and connecting aircraft controls and air traffic systems are all examples of human-automation interface challenges.

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